

VALIDATION AND EFFECTIVENESS OF WORKBOOK-BASED APPROACH FOR FUNDAMENTALS OF ACCOUNTANCY, BUSINESS, AND MANAGEMENT 1

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Validation and Effectiveness of Workbook-Based Approach for Fundamentals of Accountancy, Business, and Management 1

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Abstract

The need for effective instructional material in teaching Fundamentals Accountancy, Business and Management 1 (FABM1) stresses the demand for innovative approaches to address the challenges students face in mastering accounting concepts and skills. This action research aimed to validate and assess the effectiveness of a workbook-based approach in teaching FABM 1, addressing challenges faced by students. The workbook-based approach was developed in response to DepEd Order No. 37, series of 2022, in the context of disruptions caused by extreme weather conditions and other calamities and aligns with the K to 12 Curriculum and Most Essential Learning Competencies. An action research design was employed to validate and assess the effectiveness of the workbook by eight (8) purposively selected experts who evaluated its content, format, and presentation, and organization using the adapted checklist based on the Learning Resources Management and Development System of the Department of Education (DepEd-LRMDS) Technical Specifications for Print Resources, along with eighty (80) students from Morong National Senior High School. Pre-test and post-test assessments were conducted to compare the workbook-based learning intervention with traditional teaching methods. The results showed that the workbook received a "very satisfactory" rating across all criteria. The study further assessed its effectiveness through the use of control and experimental groups. Thus, the workbook-based approach significantly enhances student engagement, comprehension, and mastery of competencies in FABM1, making it a valuable resource for both face-to-face and modular distance learning setups, promoting consistent learning outcomes, practical application of concepts, and the overall effectiveness of instructional delivery systems.

Keywords: *workbook-based approach, FABM1, accounting*

Introduction

Learning accounting and mathematical skills remains a persistent challenge specifically among Filipino learners this indicates the need for relevant instructional material to bridge the gap and develop the skills and practical knowledge for the subject. This is evident with the claims of PISA and UNESCO, that educational preparation demonstrates a gap in practice training and limited education resources. Developing learning materials is essential to equip students with competencies and skills, especially in subjects that have significant impacts on their future career path, particularly Fundamentals of Accountancy, Business, and Management 1, this suggests a workbook-based approach to reinforce mastery, analytical thinking, and develop numerical literacy skills. Fundamentals in Accountancy, Business, and Management 1 (FABM 1) serves as a foundation for understanding a business.

Many traditional textbooks focus on wordy information that hinders students' appreciation of Basic Accounting. According to Martínez and Perez (2020), an experiential learning approach, which included guided practice through workbooks, enhanced engagement, and deepened comprehension by allowing students to apply theoretical concepts directly. Despite the considerable potential of workbook-based methodologies, research proving their efficacy remains limited, particularly within the Philippine education system, where resources are mostly allocated to lecture-based instructional strategies.

Meanwhile, Santos (2022) highlighted that workbook activities promote active learning and student engagement by breaking down complex tasks into manageable parts, which is critical for subjects like Fundamentals of Accountancy, Business, and Management 1 (FABM1), where a solid grasp of Basic Accounting is necessary in preparation for college and real-life applications, thereby catering to students with different strengths and improving retention and understanding.

In response to the DepEd's goal for accessible and relevant education, as articulated in DepEd Order No. 37, series of 2022, which emphasized the need for contextualized and flexible learning resources due to disruptions caused by the extreme weather conditions and other calamities and aligns with the K to 12 Curriculum and Most Essential Learning Competencies.. The workbook-based approach addressed this need by allowing flexibility, particularly in modular distance learning setups, thus ensuring that students' learning continuity, it corresponds with the Department of Education's (DepEd) K to 12 Curriculum for Senior High School and the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs), including understanding various accounting concepts and principles, applying the Accounting Equation, classifying accounts, recording and posting business transactions, completing the Accounting Cycle for service and merchandising businesses, and analyzing financial statements.

However, implementing a workbook-based curriculum posed several challenges. The primary concern was ensuring that the workbook's content, format, and presentation were aligned with the Department of Education's existing curriculum standards for Senior High School and effectively addressed the learning competencies in FABM 1, to contribute to a more tailored, engaging, and effective instructional approach. Moreover, it highlighted the importance of innovative and adaptable resources that meet the diverse needs of

learners, thereby supporting DepEd's mission to promote equitable, culture-based, and quality basic education. According to Lee and Thompson (2021), a successful validation process involves collecting and analyzing data to measure the workbook's effectiveness on students' academic achievements and skill acquisition.

Research Questions

This study primarily aimed to validate and test the effectiveness of the Workbook-based Approach for Fundamentals of Accountancy, Business, and Management 1. Specifically, this sought to answer the following research questions:

1. How do the experts evaluate the developed workbook-based approach for teaching Fundamentals of Accountancy, Business, and Management 1 (FABM 1) with respect to:
 - 1.1. content;
 - 1.2. format; and
 - 1.3. presentation and organization?
2. How do the control and experimental groups perform before and after the exposure to the workbook-based approach?
3. Is there a significant difference in the level of performance of the two groups of respondents exposed and unexposed to the workbook-based approach in terms of their learning outcomes, as revealed in the pretest and post-test results?

Literature Review

Content

This study is anchored in the Cognitive Load Theory as outlined by Sweller (2020), who emphasized the importance of effective instructional design in optimizing learning processes. The theory suggested that learners had a limited capacity for processing information and that the content of the learning materials should minimize unnecessary cognitive load.

Additionally, Mayer (2020) asserted that learning materials must be crafted to minimize cognitive load while enhancing clarity and relevance. Content validation is a fundamental aspect of workbook development that improves learning efficacy in FABM 1. Incorporating these aspects in content development can refine materials to enhance comprehension, retention, and mastery.

Constructivist Learning Theory articulated by Bruner (2021) highlighted that content should allow students to construct knowledge relatable to the present environment and experiences while students actively engage with and apply the Generally Accepted Accounting Principles (GAAP).

Format

Klein and Wyss (2022) pointed out that the structural design of printed learning materials, such as format. Similarly, Baker, et al. (2021) expressed the significance of effective typography and layout were also essential in enhancing the readability and comprehension of print-based learning materials. This argument aligned with the study's objective, which furnished workbook-based learning resources designed to augment knowledge acquisition. Therefore, the utilization of legible typefaces, ample line spacing, and organized material facilitate learner engagement and comprehension.

Presentation and Organization

A well-structured progression of lessons plays a significant role in fostering student engagement and supporting a deeper understanding of the competencies. Klein and Wyss (2022) emphasized the logical sequencing and structural organization of printed learning materials.

Moreover, Sweller (2020) suggested that learning is most effective when new information is presented clearly and organized, enabling learners to connect new and existing knowledge. This principle is relevant to the workbook-based approach, as it allows a systematic presentation of Basic Accounting concepts in manageable segments by chunking the Accounting Cycle into a step-by-step process, evident in the presented activities from the workbook. Additionally, Jones and Smith (2022) asserted that the thoughtful presentation and organization of learning materials are important to enhance engagement and comprehension. It encompasses the value of structuring materials to scaffold learning, support problem-solving, and align with learners' prior knowledge.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized an action research design to validate and assess the effectiveness of the Workbook-Based Approach for the Fundamentals of Accountancy, Business, and Management 1 (FABM 1). As per Mujis, D. (2020), the primary goal of quantitative research is to provide measurable outcomes, ensuring its validity and effectiveness, reliability, and relevance in enhancing the students' learning outcomes. This approach provides a comparative analysis between workbook-based learning and a traditional method.

Respondents

The study used a purposive sampling technique in determining its participants. As stated by Benoot et al. (2019), this technique is the

deliberate choice of the participants based on their relevance to the research objectives and was chosen for their expertise and experience in teaching ABM subjects, particularly FABM 1 and Language, to confirm alignment with educational standards and relevance to student learning. It is a non-random technique that does not require computation to get a set number of participants. The material was validated by eight (8) distinguished experts, chosen based on their availability and willingness to participate, enriching the evaluation process of the workbook's effectiveness.

The research took place at Morong National Senior High School (MNSHS), a public senior high school in the Province of Rizal. The study involved two (2) sections, identified as the control group and the experimental group. A total of eighty (80) participants will be included, with approximately forty (40) students in each group. This strategic distribution ensures balanced representation, enabling a comprehensive evaluation of the workbook-based approach's effectiveness on learning outcomes in the Fundamentals of Accountancy, Business, and Management 1 (FABM 1) subject.

Instrument

A questionnaire checklist was adapted from the Learning Resources Management and Development System (LRMDS) Technical Specifications for Print Resources of the Department of Education. This checklist was used to evaluate the Workbook for Fundamentals of Accountancy, Business, and Management 1, focusing on content, format, and presentation, and organization. Each variable was measured using a four-point scale by Likert.

Procedure

The data-gathering process followed a structured methodology to ensure the validity of the findings. The workbook, developed based on the competencies outlined in the K to 12 Curriculum Guide for FABM1, underwent expert validation by eight (8) selected teachers. This group included three (3) Master Teachers and three (3) Teachers from the ABM Strand, as well as one (1) Master Teacher and one (1) Teacher in English from the Province of Rizal. The researcher adapted the questionnaire checklist from the Learning Resources Management and Development System (LRMDS) Technical Specifications for Print Resources of the Department of Education. This checklist was used to evaluate the Workbook for Fundamentals of Accountancy, Business, and Management 1, focusing on content, format, and presentation, and organization.

After the administration of the aforementioned checklist, the administration of the adopted pre-test from the developed workbook for Fundamentals of Accountancy, Business, and Management 1 (FABM1) was done. The researcher employed cluster sampling to select two sections from MNSHS for the preliminary phase. A sixty-item (60) pretest was administered to evaluate the students' knowledge and skills in FABM1. Based on the pretest item analysis, the experimental group received the workbook-based learning intervention, while the control group continued with the traditional teaching approach. Following the intervention period, both groups completed a posttest to assess the effectiveness of the workbook-based approach. Subsequently, the researcher collected and tallied the data through assessment results. Specifically, a comparison of pretest and post-test scores to support the validity of the results.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations are fundamental to ensure the integrity and respect for all individuals involved in the research. This study emphasized the importance of obtaining voluntary, informed consent from all participants, ensuring they were aware of their rights, the study's objectives, and the potential impact of their involvement. The research also prioritized the confidentiality and security of participant data. Additionally, the researcher maintained a commitment to fairness, ensuring that the research process was free from any bias or favoritism, which could potentially compromise the validity and credibility of the study's findings.

Results and Discussion

This research generated the following results with corresponding discussions of interpretations.

Evaluation of the Teacher-Experts on the Developed Workbook-based Approach for Teaching Fundamentals of Accountancy, Business, and Management 1 (FABM 1) with respect to Content, Format, and Presentation and Organization

Table 1 presents the Evaluation of the Teacher-experts on the Developed Workbook-based Approach for Teaching Fundamentals of Accountancy, Business, and Management 1 (FABM 1) with respect to Content. It could be gleaned that all items that fall under this variable were given a verbal interpretation of "Very Satisfactory".

As indicated in the table, the content of the Developed Workbook attained an overall mean score of 3.85, which was verbally interpreted as "Very Satisfactory." Significantly, a mean score of 4.00, which was verbally interpreted as "Very Satisfactory" was attained by "Content is suitable to the student's level of development." indicating enhanced understanding, retention, and mastery without overwhelming the student with excessive information.

Results indicated that the rest of the indicators under content were also perceived by the experts as Very Satisfactory, as reflected in their mean ratings ranging from 3.75-3.88. This indicates that the content of the Workbook for Fundamentals of Accountancy, Business, and Management 1 (FABM 1) was determined to have supported learning efficacy by enhancing comprehension, retention, and mastery of the competencies of DepEd, aligned with its mission to promote equitable, culture-based, and quality basic education.

Furthermore, the activities included in the workbook were thoughtfully crafted based on the feedback of the target users. Integrating guided steps and easy-to-follow templates ensured that the workbook was engaging, which enhanced comprehension, retention, and mastery of the competencies.

Table 1. Evaluation of the Teacher-Experts on the Developed Workbook-based Approach for Teaching Fundamentals of Accountancy, Business, and Management 1 (FABM 1) with respect to Content

Content	Mean	Interpretation
1. Content is suitable to the student's level of development	4.00	Very Satisfactory
2. Material contributes to the achievement of specific objectives of the subject area and grade/year level for which it is intended.	3.88	Very Satisfactory
3. Material provides for the development of higher cognitive skills such as critical thinking, creativity, learning by doing, inquiry, problem solving, etc.	3.75	Very Satisfactory
4. Material is free of ideological, cultural, religious, racial, and gender biases and prejudices.	3.88	Very Satisfactory
5. Material enhances the development of desirable values and traits such as desire for excellence, critical thinking, and productive work.	3.75	Very Satisfactory
Overall	3.85	Very Satisfactory

The results further implied that the content of the developed workbook achieved the desired improvement in learning efficacy, comprehension, retention, and mastery of the targeted competencies. The said implication is similar to the Cognitive Load Theory (Sweller, 2020), emphasized that the material must provide appropriate content to enhance learning efficacy to reduce extraneous cognitive load.

Table 2 shows the Evaluation of the Teacher-experts on the Developed Workbook-based Approach for Teaching Fundamentals of Accountancy, Business, and Management 1 (FABM 1) with respect to Format. It could be observed that all items that fall under this variable were given a verbal interpretation of “Very Satisfactory”.

As presented in the table, the Format of the Developed Workbook attained an overall mean score of 3.88, which was verbally interpreted as “Very Satisfactory.” Significantly, a mean score of 4.00, which was verbally interpreted as “Very Satisfactory” was attained by “Print size of letters is appropriate to the intended user”, “Spaces between letters and words facilitate reading”, “Font is easy to read”, “Design and layout is simple”, Paper used contributes to easy reading., and “Durable binding to withstand frequent use.”

The experts also perceived the rest of the indicators under format as Very Satisfactory, as reflected on their mean ratings ranging from 3.50-3.88. This indicates that the format of the Workbook for Fundamentals of Accountancy, Business, and Management 1 (FABM 1) was determined to have supported learning efficacy by selecting effective typography, layout, and visual design in enhancing the readability and comprehension of printed texts.

Thus improving comprehension, retention, and mastery of the competencies of DepEd, aligned with its mission to promote equitable, culture-based, and quality basic education.

Furthermore, the activities included in the workbook were thoughtfully designed, and the workbook’s format supports readability, ease of use, and durability, making it a practical learning material.

The results further indicated that the format of the developed workbook for Fundamentals of Accountancy, Business, and Management 1 (FABM 1) was a user-centered instructional design. The readable fonts and well-structured templates allowed students to actively engage in the learning process. The said implication is similar to what Baker, et al. (2021) mentioned that materials must have effective typography, and layout to enhance the readability and comprehension of printed learning material.

Table 2. Evaluation of the Teacher-Experts on the Developed Workbook-based Approach for Teaching Fundamentals of Accountancy, Business, and Management 1 (FABM 1) with respect to Format

Format	Mean	Interpretation
Prints		
1. Size of letters is appropriate to the intended user.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
1.2 Spaces between letters and words facilitate reading.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
1.3 Font is easy to read.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
2. Design and Layout		
2.1 Attractive and pleasing to look at.	3.88	Very Satisfactory
2.2 Simple (i.e., does not distract the attention of the reader)	4.00	Very Satisfactory
2.3 Adequate illustration in relation to text	3.50	Very Satisfactory
3. Paper and Binding		
3.1 Paper used contributes to easy reading.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
3.2 Durable binding to withstand frequent use.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
4. Size and Weight of Resource		
4.1 Easy to handle	3.88	Very Satisfactory
4.2 Relatively light	3.50	Very Satisfactory
Overall	3.88	Very Satisfactory

Table 3 exhibits the Evaluation of the Teacher-experts on the Developed Workbook-based Approach for Teaching Fundamentals of Accountancy, Business, and Management 1 (FABM 1) with respect to Presentation and Organization. It could be implied that all items that fall under this variable were given a verbal interpretation of “Very Satisfactory”.

Table 3. *Evaluation of the Teacher-Experts on the Developed Workbook-based Approach for Teaching Fundamentals of Accountancy, Business, and Management 1 (FABM 1) with respect to Presentation and Organization*

<i>Presentation and Organization</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. Presentation is engaging, interesting, and understandable.	3.88	Very Satisfactory
2. There is logical and smooth flow of ideas.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
3. Vocabulary level is adapted to target reader’s likely experience and level of understanding.	4.00	Very Satisfactory
4. Length of sentences is suited to the comprehension level of the target reader.	3.88	Very Satisfactory
Overall	3.94	Very Satisfactory

As presented in the table, Presentation and Organization of the Developed Workbook attained an overall mean score of 3.94, which was verbally interpreted as “Very Satisfactory.” Significantly, a mean score of 4.00, which was verbally interpreted as “Very Satisfactory,” was attained by “There is a logical and smooth flow of ideas.”, and “Vocabulary level is adapted to target reader’s likely experience and level of understanding.”

Meanwhile, the rest of the indicators under presentation and organization were also perceived by the experts as Very Satisfactory, as reflected in their mean rating was 3.88. This indicates that the presentation and organization of the Workbook for Fundamentals of Accountancy, Business, and Management 1 (FABM 1) was determined to have supported learning efficacy by providing a well-organized, clear, and logical presentation of competencies. Thus improving comprehension, retention, and mastery of the competencies of DepEd, aligned with its mission to promote equitable, culture-based, and quality basic education.

Furthermore, the activities included in the workbook were organized and presented in a logical sequence, ensuring that the students could follow the flow of ideas seamlessly. The workbook’s presentation and organization supported the development of mastery by providing clear, engaging, and logical, making it a user-friendly learning material.

The results further implied that the presentation and organization of the developed workbook for FABM 1 was straightforward which made following instructions easier. This indicates that the presentation and organization of the workbook positively contributed to the overall flow of information, that connects previous competencies to the present one. The said implication is similar to what Mayer (2020) highlighted that well-organized instructional materials enhance clarity, and promote understanding, retention, and mastery by structuring information logically.

Table 4 reflects the Composite Table on the Evaluation of the Teacher-experts on the Developed Workbook-based Approach for Teaching Fundamentals of Accountancy, Business, and Management 1 (FABM 1). It could be confirmed from the table that Presentation and Organization got the highest mean, followed by Format with 3.88 and Content with 3.85. All of them are verbally interpreted as Very Satisfactory, with the Grand Mean of 3.89. Results affirmed that the developed Workbook for Fundamentals of Accountancy, Business, and Management 1 (FABM 1) can be used as a learning material.

Table 4. *Composite Table on the Evaluation of the Teacher-Experts on the Developed Workbook-based Approach for Teaching Fundamentals of Accountancy, Business, and Management 1 (FABM 1)*

<i>Factor</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. Content	3.85	Very Satisfactory
2. Format	3.88	Very Satisfactory
3. Presentation and Organization	3.94	Very Satisfactory
Grand Mean	3.89	Very Satisfactory

The results of the study corroborate Mayer (2020), who asserted that well-structured instructional materials reduce cognitive strain and enhance learning among students. The results coincide with the study conducted by Bruner (2021), which demonstrated that using the developed workbook significantly increases the students’ comprehension and retention. Baker, Smith, and Sutcliffe (2021) asserted that the format and presentation of educational materials must be engaging and accessible to learners. These findings endorse the effectiveness of utilizing the workbook as an educational tool to improve reading comprehension, retention, and mastery of the competencies associated with FABM 1.

Level of Performance of the Control and Experimental Group in Fundamentals of Accountancy, Business, and Management 1 Before and After Exposure to the Developed Workbook-based Approach

Table 5 reveals the test results that both the control and experimental groups improved their performance; the experimental group, exposed to the workbook-based approach, demonstrated significantly greater improvement, as observed in the mean score from 13.23 to 48.55, with a substantial reduction in variability. In contrast, the control group, which did not receive any intervention, showed a minimal increase in mean score from 14.23 to 37.68, it was also observed that variability decreased but to a lesser extent as compared with the other group. This highlighted the effectiveness of the workbook-based approach in enhancing mastery of the competencies.

Results support the study of Bergmann, J. (2023), which emphasizes structured interventions to ensure all learners achieve mastery. Students were able to finish the task within the allotted time, highlighting the effectiveness of the workbook-based approach, as revealed in their post-test scores.

Table 5. *Level of Performance of the Control and Experimental Group in Fundamentals of Accountancy, Business, and Management 1 Before and After Exposure to the Developed Workbook-based Approach*

Group	Before			After		
	Mean	Sd.	Variance	Mean	Sd	Variance
Control	14.23	10.43	108.79	37.68	5.38	28.94
Experimental	13.23	7.25	52.56	48.55	2.48	6.15

Significant Difference in the Level of Performance of Students Exposed and Unexposed to the Workbook-based Approach in Terms of Their Learning Outcomes, as Revealed in The Pretest and Post-test Results

Table 6 shows the comparison between the control and experimental group's pretest scores, the p-values for both groups are 0.057. This means that the null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted. This indicates that there is no significant difference between the pretest results in both groups.

The post-test results of the control and experimental group indicate the p-values for both groups are 0.00. This means that the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected. This indicates that there is a significant difference between the post-test results in both groups. However, in terms of mastery of competencies, it could be observed that the mean score of the experimental group is much higher than the control group, the Learning Outcome Assessment (LOA) Results would reveal that all students are at mastery level. The control group revealed that twenty-one (21) students were at mastery level, eighteen (18) students were nearing mastery level, and one student was at unmastered level. Furthermore, the variance analysis showed that the experimental group had a lower variance (6.15) compared to the control group (28.94), indicating greater consistency in learning outcomes for students using the workbook-based approach.

Additionally, the study of Utami et al. (2020), highlights the use of workbooks positively improves student's learning effectiveness. This justifies and sustains the importance of the workbook-based approach in the teaching-learning process and maximizes the student's comprehension and mastery of the competencies.

Table 6. *Significant Difference in the Level of Performance of Students Exposed and Unexposed to the Workbook-based Approach in Terms of Their Learning Outcomes, as Revealed in the Pretest and Post-test Results*

Group		Mean	SD	p-value	H_0	Interpretation
Control	Before	14.23	10.43	0.057	R	S
Experimental		13.23	7.25			
Control	After	37.68	5.38	0.000	R	S
Experimental		48.55	2.48			

Conclusions

Based on the findings, it was concluded that the Workbook-based Approach for Fundamentals of Accountancy, Business, and Management 1 was accepted based on the evaluation of the experts. The effectiveness of the workbook-based approach is highlighted by the significant improvement in the experimental group's post-test scores, indicating mastery of the competencies. Therefore, the material can be used as a learning tool.

Based on the conclusion, it is recommended that the workbook-based approach be implemented in Morong National Senior High School. Additionally, regular updates to the material should be made to ensure conformity with the current curriculum implemented by the Department of Education for Senior High School. Furthermore, continuous feedback must be collected from the stakeholders to further refine the material to ensure that the workbook remains relevant and effective as a learning tool. It is also recommended that a Teachers' Guide or Manual must be made available in reference to the workbook developed.

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